

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

Peer-reviewed publications

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Call: H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Work Programmes:

H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth

H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 7.9

6 publications in peer reviewed journals

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Summary

This document is a list of finalized and planned peer-reviewed publications produced by the MATILDE project. The list is divided into journal articles, books/monographs, and individual chapters.

The list reflects the status in the last project month (January 2023). Publication activity will continue after the official end of the project.

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Introduction

The Project planned to publish at least 6 articles in top-tier peer-reviewed journals. To date, 10 peer-reviewed articles have been published or are being finalized. In addition, the project is preparing 6 peer-reviewed edited volumes. Given the nature of academic publishing, more publications (including peer-reviewed journal articles) will follow after the project's closing date.

MATILDE has made a commitment to produce high-quality and high-impact research. This means following good academic practices rigidly and collaborating with reputable publishers. According to the rules set up by the European Commission, MATILDE has published in line with H2020 Open Access rules.

In addition to peer-reviewed publication, MATILDE has also published resources for non-academics, such as *The Self-Assessment Toolbox for Practitioners and Policy Makers*. MATILDE teams also engaged traditional and new media, including national circulation news media, local newspapers, podcasts and other. These activities are described in more detail in the report *Journalistic Coverage of MATILDE Results*.

Peer-reviewed journal papers

1. Davydova-Minguet, Olga and Pöllänen, Pirjo. (2022). The unbearable lightness of everyday border: Meanings of closeness of the border for Russian-speaking immigrants in the Finnish border area. *Barents Studies*, Vol 7(1). 59-79. [Available here](#).
2. Gilli M. (2022), New Mountain Populations. Migrants and the Attractiveness of Alpine Territories. *Fuori Luogo. Rivista di Sociologia del Territorio, Turismo, Tecnologia*. 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.6093/2723-9608/8929>
3. Gruber, M., Lardiés-Bosque, R., /Membretti, A. & Tonelli, D. (2021): The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on remote and rural regions of Europe: Foreign immigration and local Development. In: *GSSI – Discussion Paper Series in Regional Science & Economic Geography*, Nr. 2021-15. [https://www.gssi.it/images/DPRSEG_2021-15%20\(1\).pdf](https://www.gssi.it/images/DPRSEG_2021-15%20(1).pdf).
4. Kaya, Ayhan (2023). “The Neoliberal Face of the ‘Local Turn’ in Governance of Refugees in Turkey: Participatory Action Research in Karacabey, Bursa,” *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, Special Issue on Welcoming Spaces.
5. Krasteva, Anna (2021). “Balkan migration crises and beyond.” In: *Southeastern Europe*, 45, 173-203. doi:10.30965/18763332-45020001
6. Machold, I., Bauchinger, L., Dax, T. (2022): ‘Integration pathways of forced migrants in rural settings. Access to resources and agency’. *Societal changes and their implications on agri-food systems and rural areas. Proceedings of the Joint Conference of the Slovenian Association of Agricultural Economists (DAES) and the Austrian Association of Agricultural Economists (ÖGA)*. 22-23 September 2022, p. 61-62. <http://www.daes.si/sl/zbornik>
7. Manahl, Caroline (2022). Soziale Teilhabe geflüchteter Menschen in ländlichen Gemeinden: eine gendersensible Analyse der Bedeutung lokaler Rahmenbedingungen (Social participation of refugees in rural communities: a

gender-sensitive analysis of the importance of the local context; submission to the *Berliner Journal für Soziologie*.

8. Rauhut Kompaniets, O. & Rauhut, D. (2022) Place Brand, Public Diplomacy and Refugee Immigration. To be submitted to *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*.
9. Rauhut, D. (2020) Integration and informal institutions. *Society* 57(2): 211–218 DOI: 10.1007/s12115-020-00467-6
10. Yılmaz Elmas, F. and A. Kaya (2022) “Kırsal Bölgelerde Göçmenlerin İşgücü Piyasasına Katılımı ve Yerel Ekonomiye Etkisi: Karacabey Örneği” [The Labor Market Participation of Immigrants in Rural Areas and its Impact on the Local Economy: Karacabey as a Case Study], *Çalışma ve Toplum*, 2022/4, No. 75 (in Turkish).

Peer-reviewed books

1. Caputo M. L., Bianchi M., Baglioni S., (eds) (2023). *Newcomers in the Economy of European Rural and Mountain Areas. A Cross-country Comparative Analysis of Migrants’ Socio-economic Impact* (book proposal in English, Springer-IMISCOE)
2. Krasteva, Anna and Evelina Staykova (eds) (2023). *Migration and local development: reterritorialization and revitalization of remote regions. The example of Harmanli and Haskovo region* (in Bulgarian)
3. Laine, J., Rauhut, D. & Gruber, M. – eds. (2022) *Renegotiating Remoteness: Assessing the Social Impact of Immigration in Europe*. Edward Elgar.
4. Rauhut, D., Aigner-Walder, B. & Schomaker, R. (2023). *The Economics of Immigration to Cities and Regions: Theoretical Perspectives and Empirical Insights*. [Palgrave Macmillan].
5. Rauhut, D. (ed.) (2023). *Remoteness and immigrant integration: Exploring new theoretical and methodological perspectives*. Edward Elgar Publisher.
6. Membretti, A., A. Krasteva & T. Dax (eds.) (2022). *The Renaissance of Remote Places. Migration and Resilience in European Mountain and Rural Regions*. London: Routledge.

Peer-reviewed book chapters

1. Aigner-Walder, B./Gruber, M./Schomaker, R. (2022): Thesis 5: Migration impact assessment as a powerful tool for evaluating the comprehensive effects of migration on local societies and economies. In: Membretti, A./Dax, T./Krasteva, A. (Eds.): *The Renaissance of Remote Place. MATILDE Manifesto*, Routledge, pp. 51-59. DOI: 10.4324/9781003260486-8.
2. Caputo M. L., Bianchi M., Baglioni S. (2023). "Integrating remote regions. How remoteness affects migrants and local communities' integration process" In Rauhut D. (ed) *Remoteness and immigrant integration: New theoretical perspectives and methodological insights* (Book proposal in English);
3. Dalla Torre C., Gori, F., Membretti, A., Ravazzoli E. (2022), *Pratiques de commoning et stewardship pour la gestion des ressources dans les territoires de montagne dans un contexte en changement. Exploration d'études de cas dans le Trentino, Italie*, in Vous avez dit espace commun? Publisher: Peter Lang.
4. Dax, T., Dalla Torre, C. and Machold, I. (2022): Thesis 3: It is time for a new rural and mountain narrative. In: Membretti, A., Dax, T. and Krasteva, A. (eds.): *The Renaissance of Remote Places. MATILDE manifesto*. Abingdon: Routledge.
5. Doğan Yenisey, Kübra, and Koray Akay (*Forthcoming*), "Labour Market Impact of Migration in Bursa", in Simone Baglioni and Maria Caputo (et al.), *Economic Impact of Migration* (to be submitted)
6. Gilli M. and Membretti A. (2022). *Migrants and local economies in Italian mountain areas: what opportunity for innovation?* in Caputo M.L., Bianchi M. and Baglioni S., *Newcomers in the Economy of European Rural and Mountain Areas. A Cross-country Comparative Analysis of Migrants' Socio-economic Impact*.
7. Gruber M., Lardies-Bosque R., Membretti A. and Tonelli D. (2022), *The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on remote and rural regions of Europe: Foreign immigration and local development*, in GSSI Discussion paper No.2021-15 November 2021

8. Gruber, M. & Rauhut, D. (2022). Immigrant integration – a patchwork of fragmented responsibilities, multi-level governance and New Public Management. In: Laine, J., Rauhut, D. & Gruber, M. (eds.) *Renegotiating remoteness: Towards enhanced social impact of immigration*.
9. Gruber, M. & Rauhut, D. (2022): Immigrant integration in Austria and Sweden – a patchwork of multilevel governance and fragmented responsibilities. Laine, J., Rauhut, D. & Gruber, M. (eds.): Laine, J., Rauhut, D. & Gruber, M. (eds.) *Renegotiating remoteness: Towards enhanced social impact of immigration*. Edward Elgar (accepted for publication, English)
10. Gruber, M. & Zupan, K. (2022): Arbeitsmarktbedingte Herausforderungen und Potentiale der COVID-19 Pandemie für Migrant*innen in Österreich. In: Pichler, C. & Küffner, C. (eds.): *Arbeit, Prekariat und Covid-19*. SpringerNature, pp. 71-98
11. Gruber, M. & Zupan, K. (2022): Auswirkungen internationaler Zuwanderung auf die wirtschaftliche und regionale Entwicklung in Kärnten. In: Anderwald, K., Hren, K. & Stainer-Hämmerle, K. (eds.): *Kärntner Jahrbuch für Politik 2022*. Mohorjeva Hermagoras (forthcoming, German)
12. Gruber, M. & Zupan, K.: Impacts of international immigration on the economic and regional development of rural areas – the example of Carinthia. In: Krasteva, A. & Staikova, E. (eds.): *Migration and local development: territorialization and revitalization of remote regions. On the example of Harmanli and the Haskovo region*. (forthcoming, Bulgarian)
13. Gruber, M. (2023): Transculturism and post-migrant narratives in rural areas: A conceptual approach. In: Rauhut, D. (ed.) *Remoteness and immigrant integration: Exploring new theoretical and methodological perspectives*. Edward Elgar (forthcoming, English)
14. Gruber, M., Zupan, K., del Olmo-Vicén, N. & Lardiés-Bosque, R. (2022): Labour market shortages and exclusion practices: The irrationalities of the labour markets and the legislation. In: Laine, J., Rauhut, D. & Gruber, M. (eds.): *Renegotiating remoteness:*

Towards enhanced social impact of immigration. Edward Elgar (accepted for publication, English)

15. Gruber, M./del Olmo-Vicén, N./Lardiés-Bosque, R. (2022): Thesis 10: The COVID-19 pandemic: threats and opportunities for remote, rural and mountain regions of Europe, and for their inhabitants, In: Membretti, A./Dax, T./Krasteva, A. (Eds.): The Renaissance of Remote Place. MATILDE Manifesto, Routledge, pp. 92-100. DOI: 10.4324/9781003260486-13.
16. Gruber, M.; Lardiés-Bosque, R.; Membretti, A. & Tonelli, D. (2021): “The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on remote and rural regions of Europe: Foreign immigration and local development”. *GSSI Discussion Paper series in Regional Science & Economic Geography*. Discussion paper No. 2021-15, November 2021, 38 pp. [https://www.gssi.it/images/DPRSEG_2021-15%20\(1\).pdf](https://www.gssi.it/images/DPRSEG_2021-15%20(1).pdf)
17. Gruber, Marika, Nuria del Olmo-Vicén and Raúl Lardiés-Bosque Thesis 10. Immigrants in rural and mountain areas of Europe in the light of the (post) COVID-19 pandemic (Chapter of the MANIFESTO book).
18. Hansson, U. and Lund, Per Olav, Structures, trends and turning points of Norwegian and Swedish integration policies, in Laine, J., Rauhut, D. and Gruber, M. Renegotiating remoteness: Towards enhanced social impact of immigration. *[In: Book proposal]*
19. Hansson, U., Machold, I., Dax, T. and Lund, P.O (2022). International Migration to Rural and Mountain Areas is an important but neglected phenomenon. In: Membretti, A., Krasteva, A. and Dax, T. (eds), The Renaissance of Remote Places. Migration and Resilience in European Mountain and Rural Regions. MATILDE Manifesto. Routledge
20. Hansson, U., Machold, I., Dax, T. and Lund, Per-Olav, International Migration to Rural and Mountain Areas is an important but neglected phenomenon. In: Membretti, A., Krasteva, A. and Dax, T. (eds), The Renaissance of Remote Places. Migration and Resilience in European Mountain and Rural Regions. MATILDE Manifesto. *Forthcoming*.
21. Hansson, U., Macuchova, Z, Akin, D., and Lund, P.O. (2022). Structures, trends and turning points of Norwegian and Swedish integration policies, in Laine, J., Rauhut, D.

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22. Kaya, A., Stenbacka, S. and Krasteva, A. Rural-Urban relationships are a fundamental asset in terms of policies aiming at the inclusion of remote places within a metro-montane framework. In: Membretti, A., Krasteva, A. and Dax, T. (eds), *The Renaissance of Remote Places. Migration and Resilience in European Mountain and Rural Regions. MATILDE Manifesto. Forthcoming.*
 23. Kaya, A., Weidinger, T. & F. Yılmaz-Elmas (2021): *Tarımsal ve Dağlık Bölgelerde Mekânsal Özellikler ve Uluslararası Göçmenlerin Dağılımı: Bursa ve Karacebey Özelinde Türkiye.* Marmara Municipalities Union: Istanbul.
 24. Kaya, A., Weidinger, T. & F. Yılmaz-Elmas (2021): *Tarımsal ve Dağlık Bölgelerde Mekânsal Özellikler ve Uluslararası Göçmenlerin Dağılımı: Bursa ve Karacebey Özelinde Türkiye.* Marmara Municipalities Union: Istanbul.
 25. Kaya, Ayhan (2022). Local Turn in Migrant Integration Practices of Turkey: Syrians in Bursa. In: Laine, J., Rauhut, D. & Gruber, M. (eds.) *Renegotiating remoteness: Towards enhanced social impact of immigration.*
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 27. Kaya, Ayhan (2022), "AB-Türkiye Göç Mutabakatı: Tampon Ülke?" (EU-Turkey Refugee Statement: Buffer Zone?), *TÜSİAD Turkish Business Association Working Paper Series* (March), Istanbul <https://tusiad.org/tr/yayinlar/raporlar/item/10937-tusi-ad-kuresel-siyaset-forumu-makale-dizisi-no-2-ab-turkiye-multeci-mutabakati-tampon-ulke> (in Turkish)
 28. Kordel, S. & Weidinger, T. (2022): Economic impact of TCNs in rural Bavaria, Germany. In: Baglioni, S. & M.L. Caputo (Eds.): *TBA* (= Routledge Studies on Remote Places and Remoteness 2). Routledge: London.
 29. Kordel, S., Weidinger, T., Machold, I. & Gruber, M. (2022): Appropriate housing in rural and mountain areas? Current structures and practices of access for immigrants. The

- example of Alpine regions in Austria and Germany. In: Laine, J., Rauhut, D. & Gruber, M. (eds.): *Renegotiating remoteness: Towards enhanced social impact of immigration*. Edward Elgar (accepted for publication, English)
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31. Krasteva, A., Membretti, A. and Dax, T. (2022): Reconstruction of remoteness as a new centrality and dialogical cocreation of living together. In: Membretti, A., Dax, T. and Krasteva, A. (eds.): *The Renaissance of Remote Places. MATILDE manifesto*. Abingdon: Routledge.
32. Krasteva, Anna (2022). De/Re/Bordering Remoteness in Time of Crisis: (Mis)Management of Heterogeneous Migrations in the Rhodope Mountain. In: *Jussi Laine and Daniel Rauhut (Eds) Renegotiating remoteness: Towards enhanced social impact of immigration*
33. Laine, J. (2023). Participation beyond integration. In: Rauhut, D. (ed.) *Remoteness and immigrant integration: Exploring new theoretical and methodological perspectives*.
34. Lardiés-Bosque, R. & Membretti, A. (2022). "In-migration to European mountain regions: a challenge for local resilience and sustainable development", in Stefan Schneiderbauer, Jorg Szarzynski & John F. Shroder (Eds.): *Safeguarding Mountains: a Global Challenge*. Elsevier Science, Bolzano, 350 pp. ISBN: 0128220953, 9780128220955
35. Machold, I., Bauchinger, L. and Dax, T. (2022) Integration pathways of forced migrants in rural settings. Access to resources and agency. DAES-ÖGA Proceedings: Paper presented at the DAES-ÖGA Conference, 22 – 23 September 2022 in Ljubljana. Slovenia (in print).
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- eds. (2022) *Renegotiating remoteness: Towards enhanced social impact of immigration*. Cheltenham/Northampton: Edward Elgar.
37. Machold, I., Dax, T., Bauchinger, L., Hansson, U and Lund PO, Long-term integration needs: the case of Austria, Norway and Sweden, in in Laine, J., Rauhut, D. and Gruber, M. *Renegotiating remoteness: Towards enhanced social impact of immigration. [In: Book proposal]*
38. Membretti, A., Dax, T. and Krasteva, A. (2022): *The renaissance of rural, mountainous and remote regions of Europe. A call for action*. In: Membretti, A., Dax, T. and Krasteva, A. (eds.): *The Renaissance of Remote Places. MATILDE manifesto*. Abingdon: Routledge.
39. Membretti, A., Dax, T. and Machold, I. (2022): *Thesis 1: Reframing remote places and remoteness as a collective resource and value for Europe*. In: Membretti, A., Dax, T. and Krasteva, A. (eds.): *The Renaissance of Remote Places. MATILDE manifesto*. Abingdon: Routledge.
40. Rauhut, D. & Laine, J. (2023). *Theorising immigrant integration: A critical examination*. In: Rauhut, D. (ed.) *Remoteness and immigrant integration: Exploring new theoretical and methodological perspectives*.
41. Rauhut, D. (2023). *How do we measure immigrant integration? On empirical data, indicators and causality*. In: Rauhut, D. (ed.) *Remoteness and immigrant integration: Exploring new theoretical and methodological perspectives*.
42. Rauhut, D. (2023). *The methodology of immigrant integration*. In: Rauhut, D. (ed.) *Remoteness and immigrant integration: Exploring new theoretical and methodological perspectives*.
43. Stenbacka, S. & Hansson, U. *The rural core of Europe under stress – the role of migration in the recovery of rural and mountain regions*. [preliminary title] In: Membretti, A., Krasteva, A. and Dax, T. (eds), *The Renaissance of Remote Places. Migration and Resilience in European Mountain and Rural Regions. MATILDE Manifesto. Forthcoming*.

44. Stenbacka, S. and Mathisen, T. 'A spanner in the works': Understanding the relationship between state withdrawal in rural areas, refugee integration policy and social polarization. In: Lajne, J., Rauhut, D. and Gruber, M. *Renegotiating remoteness: Towards enhanced social impact of immigration. [In: Book proposal]*
45. Stenbacka, S. Integration and rural space: a multi-layered process of possibilities and obstacles. In: Rauhut, D. (ed) *Remoteness and immigrant integration: New theoretical perspectives and methodological insights. [In: Book proposal]*
46. Stenbacka, S. Internationell migration och lokal välfärd. In: Stenbacka, S., Hermelin, B., Mathisen, T. (eds.) *Goda livsvillkor för hållbar samhällsutveckling på landsbygden – nya perspektiv på service, infrastruktur och välfärd. [In: Book proposal]*
47. Uyan Semerci, P., Yılmaz Elmas, F., Lardiés Bosque, R. and Del Olmo-Vicén, N. (2022) "Access to Welfare Policies by Immigrants: Comparing Centralized and Decentralized Governance in the Examples of Turkey and Spain", in J. P. Laine, D. Rauhut and M. Gruber (eds.), *Assessing the Social Impact of Immigration in Europe: Renegotiating Remoteness*, Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd.
48. Weidinger, T. & S. Kordel (2022): International migration has to be considered as one expression among diverse mobilities. In: Membretti, A. et al. (Eds.): *Migration and Resilience in European Mountain and Rural Regions: MATILDE Manifesto* (Routledge Studies on Remote Places and Remoteness 1).Routledge: London.